

ANALYSIS OF THE STYLISTIC DEVICES IN THE FIRST CHAPTER OF THE BOOK “THE ALCHEMIST” BY PAULO COELHO.

Qo‘ziyeva Salima Qabuljonovna

Master student Samarkand State University Philology faculty

Literary translation (English language) Department

qoziyevasalima19960110@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In order to create a masterpiece any writer or author should use stylistic devices widely because they helps to grab the reader’s attention. Paulo Coelho also used a range of stylistic devices in his book which is called “The Alchemist”. In this article we will delve into some of them.

Key words: *stylistic devices, foreshadowing, simile, metaphor, symbolism, personification, metonymy.*

INTRODUCTION

Stylistic devices are specific techniques that allow a writer to convey a deeper meaning that goes beyond what’s on the page. Stylistic devices work alongside plot summary and characters to elevate a story and prompt reflection on life, society, and what it means to be human. Paulo Coelho has depicted characters acting as significant symbols in the novel. The main character of ‘Alchemist’ is not only depicted, as a simple ordinary human being, rather having symbolic weight - the man, who understands himself, the world and the religion. He symbolises spiritual attainment and understanding of the soul of the world. So that this book is a bestseller as a result of this I chose to analyze it.

MAINBODY

Foreshadowing **is** a stylistic device in which a writer gives an advance hint of what is to come later in the story. Foreshadowing often appears at the beginning of a story or a chapter and helps the reader develop expectations about the coming events in a story. “And this is my interpretation: you must go to the Pyramids in Egypt. I have never heard of them, but, if it was a child who showed them to you, they exist. There you will find a treasure that will make you a rich man.” Coelho uses this as a form of captivating the audiences attention through the use of the supernatural, but he has not given away the entirety of the plot, and therefore it is not a legit phrase in the story to give away the ending.

Simile is another type of stylistic devise which describes something by comparing it with something else using the words “as” or “like “. "Books are like caravans in that respect". The boy was saying that he learns from observing,in this case,the caravans. However, different from the boy, the English man always has a book in his hands to learn from. This is comparing books to caravans in the respect of learning. Another example of a simile is that.”.. everyone in the market fell to their knees, touched their foreheads to the ground, and took up a chant. Than, like a colony of worker ants, they dismantled their stalls and left.”

Metaphor_ a figure of speech in which a term or phrase is applied to something to which it is not literally applicable in order to suggest a resemblance."The desert is a capricious lady, and sometimes she drives men crazy." In the context of this quote the metaphor was used to define the importance and establish the understanding of how dangerous the desert is, by expressing the fact that everyone needed to listen to him carefully and follow his directions. This is effective because when comparing the desert to a capricious lady, which means that the woman is erratic and sudden, he is expressing exactly how tricky the desert can be and providing a comparison widely understood.

Symbolism is the use of symbols to represent ideas or qualities. "When you are unable to read the omens, they will help you to do so." The use of symbolism is used throughout the entirety of the book, everything that takes place is either registered as a good omen or a bad one. Santiago symbolises a simple truth of life that it should be taken as a journey in which we need to set our priorities. And one should be able to sacrifice material gains in order to attain maturity, spiritually and knowledge. For example, throughout the novel, the boy had several opportunities to quit his journey and settle down, but he preferred to continue, since he wanted to understand the universe by having a firsthand communication with it. This involvement of his soul with the elements of his nature transformed him into a dignified religious person. The Englishman wanted to explore the mysteries of the universe through science and books. Thus, Coelho has symbolised him as the man of Europe, a master in science and knowledge. He represents the scientific and technological advancements of the West. That is why throughout the novel he prefers to read the books and practice, instead of having firsthand communication with the elements of nature. The 'philosopher's stone' is a legendary alchemical substance supposedly capable of turning base metals, especially lead, into gold. It was also sometimes believed to be the elixir of life, which is useful for achieving immortality. Thus, the stone was the central symbol of the mystical terminology of alchemy, symbolising perfection, enlightenment and heavenly bliss. This symbol has been used in the novel not only to highlight Santiago's attainment of maturity and knowledge, but also to state the fact that whosoever has some materialistic approach in gaining the elixir of life can never be able to gain it. Alchemy in this novel is the symbol that refers to the whole journey, which a man undertakes to achieve the treasure at the end. It is not just material gain, but also the spiritual gain. So, Alchemist in the novel is the person, who has already undergone all the hardships in life and has achieved his treasures. Personification *is another type of stylistic device that representation of a thing or a quality as a person ,in literature or art.* "The boy felt jealous of the freedom of the

wind..." Coelho uses this device because it allows him to connect a nonhuman force to an issue in human life. "Speak to the hand that wrote all," said the sun". In real life the sun can not speak, therefore this is personification. This is the moment when the sun realized the boy's answer to his question

Metonymy is a *figure of speech* in which a concept is referred to by the name of something closely associated with that thing or concept. *This stylistic device also widely used by the author. There are some clear examples of it. There was a moment of silence so profound that it seem the city was asleep. In this example of metonymy author is referring to people of the city especially merchants and customers who are usually a lot in that bazaar and it was hustling and bustling but now it was tranquil. So that in order to describe this situation more clearly to the reader this type of literary device was used.* "He didn't want to think about the possibility that some other shepherd, with a larger flock of sheep,

had arrived there before him and asked for her hand." In this sentence also we can see another metonymy when a boy wants to marry a girl he asks her hand. Clearly not hand only he asks whether she can marry him and live together.

CONCLUSION

As other masterpiece works in this allegorical novel we can find a lot of stylistic devices. However I do not write all of them only for the first chapter otherwise it can be so long data. So you can look through them above and taste their sweetness.

REFERENCES

1. "The Alchemist" by Paulo Coelho 1998
2. "Stylistic approaches to literary translation" The University of Birmingham, November 2011
3. <https://prezi.com/p/xydyfysyxeg9/the-chemist-figurative-language/>